

Swar Manovigyan: A Deep Learning Framework for Music-Based Emotion Analysis and Mental Health Insight Generation

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Abstract — Music has traditionally been seen as a powerful controller of human emotions and psychological well-being. In spite of this, there is still a lack of literature on the automation of music-induced emotion detection and its potential use as an addition to current mental health applications. This work introduces Swar Manovigyan, an end-to-end deep learning framework which categorizes songs based on their corresponding emotions according to the arousal-valence (A-V) theory into four different emotion quadrants and provides therapeutic recommendations and personalized songs. The architecture utilizes BiLSTM neural networks which classify melodies based on their Mel-spectrograms, reaching an accuracy of 98.96% on the test data split. An empirical comparison of this model to traditional machine learning classifiers, including Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) proves the effectiveness of the sequential deep learning model. The complete web application with real-time audio analysis and AI-generated explanations is implemented using FastAPI, Next.js, and Azure OpenAI.

Keywords—Music Emotion Recognition, Bidirectional LSTM, Arousal-Valence Model, Affective Computing, Mental Health, Deep Learning, Mel-Spectrogram, Emotion Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

The link between music, emotions, and psychological well-being has started drawing increasing interest among psychologists, neuroscientists, and artificial intelligence experts. Music therapy is a mature field of study where therapists utilize music as a treatment method to treat patients' cognitive, emotional, and interpersonal issues. Nonetheless, these therapies are mostly manual, highly subjective, and only accessible by those who have the

means to undertake the therapeutic sessions. The rise of online music streaming services has opened up new avenues of opportunity. It is now possible to analyse music sonically, and translate it into human emotions and make it accessible.

Emotion detection in audio is a difficult problem to solve because of the inherently subjective aspect of music perception. Perception of happy or sad emotions through music varies depending on the listener, culture, and context. Despite these variations, psychoacoustic models like the Russell Circumplex model [1] and the arousal-valence (A-V) model provide a framework to describe emotions on a two-dimensional plane that describes a considerable amount of variance in music-emotion relationships. On this plane, arousal is described as the level of activation of the emotion (from relaxed to aroused), while valence is defined as the positive or negative feeling of the emotion experienced. As shown in Figure 1, musical clips are determined based on their location in the four quadrants of the aforementioned A-V plane.

Fig. 1. Mapping of the emotion space of arousal-valence (A-V). The four quadrants correspond to Happy/Excited (High A, High V), Angry/Stressed (High A, Low V), Calm/Peaceful (Low A, High V), and Sad/Depressed (Low A, Low V).

Swar Manovigyan —where "Swar" refers to musical notes in the Indian classical tradition and "Manovigyan" means psychology in Sanskrit—is a deep learning system that operationalizes this framework for real-world application. Given an audio recording, the system extracts a sequence of Mel-spectrogram frames, feeds them through a BiLSTM network to predict continuous arousal and valence scores, maps the resulting coordinates to one of four emotion

quadrants, and finally uses a large language model (LLM) to generate human-readable therapeutic insights and song recommendations.

The key contributions of this work are: (i) a BiLSTM-based architecture for sequential audio feature modelling that achieves near-ceiling classification accuracy; (ii) a systematic comparison with classical ML baselines on a large-scale music dataset; (iii) integration of generative AI for producing contextual therapeutic explanations; and (iv) a production-grade full-stack deployment enabling real-time analysis. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related literature. Section III describes the methodology. Section IV presents experimental results. Sections V through IX discuss implications, applications, limitations, future work, and conclusions, respectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

MER research has been divided into three major stages, namely rule-based techniques, classical ML algorithms, and deep learning approaches. Early MER studies conducted by Yang et al. [2] utilized the support vector regression approach for predicting continuous arousal and valence values using manually extracted tempo, mode, and loudness audio features. Recent investigations have found that ensemble classifiers, specifically Random Forests, outperformed other methods after including spectral, rhythmic, and harmonic feature sets [3].

The advent of deep learning has made notable contributions to MER research. The application of CNNs to spectrograms has shown that representations learned by deep neural networks outperform traditional engineered feature extraction [4]. Recurrent neural network models, in particular LSTMs, emerged as popular models for capturing temporal dependencies, which play an important role in melody and rhythm, processes not easily captured by feature vectors. BiLSTM models, which analyse sequence data by considering them from both directions, have demonstrated consistent advantages in speech and music tasks by allowing each time step to draw context from the entire sequence [5].

Hizlisoy et al. [6] showed that combining spectral and temporal features with LSTM models yielded superior results on Turkish music datasets, highlighting the cross-cultural applicability of deep sequential models. More recently, attention mechanisms and transformer-based architectures have been explored for MER, though at the cost of substantially higher computational requirements. As regards practical systems aiming for real-

time implementation using general-purpose hardware, BiLSTM models provide effective and feasible solutions.

As for affective computing and its relation to mental wellbeing, most studies to date have been conducted using physiological data sources including EEG, skin conductance, and heart rate variability [7]. A more non-intrusive solution to affective disorders can be found in music-based therapies. Combining acoustic signal analysis with therapeutic explanations – a task which becomes increasingly feasible with large language models – has not been explored much yet. As far as we know, this work is one of the first attempts at integrating BiLSTM MER with therapeutic insights generated by large language models.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Arousal-Valence Emotion Framework

This model is based on the Russell Circumplex Model of affect [1], where emotions are mapped to two-dimensional space according to arousal and valence axes. To allow for computational processing of this continuous space, it is mapped into four quadrants according to emotions' arousal and valence: (1) high arousal, high valence – happy/excited; (2) high arousal, low valence – angry/stressed; (3) low arousal, high valence – calm/peaceful; and (4) low arousal, low valence – sad/depressed. The boundaries between quadrants are determined using a normalized midpoint threshold (arousal > 0.5, valence > 0.5).

B. Dataset and Exploratory Analysis

The training dataset was compiled by processing a large Spotify music database which has metadata and audio features of over 200,000 songs representing over ten genres. Each song was rated using arousal and valence scores based on ratings from listeners. As part of the preprocessing phase, duplicates were eliminated, all continuous features were normalized between [0, 1], and labels were generated using the midpoint method explained above. Figure 3 shows four plots describing the generated dataset. First, the arousal-valence scatter plot verifies that samples span all four quadrants in adequate proportions. Second, emotion label frequency distribution shows an unbalanced distribution biased towards low arousal negative valence and high arousal positive valence classes.

Fig. 2. Data set exploratory visualization (multiple graphs). Left-top: arousal vs valence scatter plot. Right-top: emotion label distribution. Left-bottom: features correlation graph. Right-bottom: top music genres distribution.

Fig. 3. Heatmap showing the Correlation of Audio Features. Positive correlations are in red and negative correlations are in blue. Significant relationship between energy, loudness and arousal

C. Audio Feature Extraction

In the case of the BiLSTM model, the input is the audio files that have been converted into sequences of Mel-frequency spectrograms using the Librosa package. First, each audio file is read at a sample rate of 22,050 Hz and converted into a Mel-spectrogram with 128 Mel bins and hop length equal to 512. The data normalization is done by applying per-track mean-variance normalization, and the output representation is of size (T, 128), where T corresponds to the number of time frames. This sequence representation is very useful in the case of recurrent architectures, like the proposed one.

For classical machine learning models, a 110-dimensional vector of features is extracted for each audio file. It consists of the mean and standard deviation of MFCCs, chroma, spectral centroid, spectral rolloff, and zero-crossing rate. Figure 9 provides the entire correlation matrix of audio features. As it can be seen, energy and loudness are strongly correlated ($r = 0.81$). Additionally, acousticness is highly negatively correlated with both energy and arousal ($r = -0.73$, $r = -0.71$). This observation matches the intuitive psychoacoustic perception of high-energy and loud music being arousing.

D. System Architecture and Data Flow

The complete system pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2. A user submits an audio file through the Next.js frontend. The file is transmitted via a POST /analyse/upload request to the Fast API backend (server.py), which orchestrates the analysis pipeline. The audio_features.py module extracts the Mel-spectrogram sequence of shape (T, 128), which is passed to the av_regressor.py module containing the trained BiLSTM model. The model returns predicted arousal and valence values, which are mapped to an emotion quadrant. These coordinates are forwarded to azure_openai_service.py, which invokes the Azure OpenAI API to generate a therapeutic explanation. The backend assembles the final JSON response—containing the emotion label, arousal, valence, therapeutic insight, and song recommendations—which is rendered on the frontend.

Fig. 2. System data flow pipeline (sequence diagram). The diagram shows communication between the Next.js frontend, FastAPI server (server.py), audio feature extractor (audio_features.py), BiLSTM regressor (av_regressor.py), and Azure OpenAI service (azure_openai_service.py).

E. BiLSTM Model Architecture

The core deep learning model is a stacked Bidirectional LSTM network designed for regression on the A-V space. As depicted in Figure 4, the architecture consists of the following layers in sequence: (1) an InputLayer accepting tensors of shape (timesteps, num_features); (2) a Bidirectional LSTM layer with 96 units per direction (192 total), return_sequences=True; (3) Dropout at rate 0.3; (4) a second Bidirectional LSTM with 48 units per direction, return_sequences=False; (5) Dropout at rate 0.3; (6) Batch Normalization; (7) a Dense layer of 128 units with ReLU activation; (8) Dropout at rate 0.3; (9) a Dense layer of 64 units with ReLU activation; and (10) a Dense output layer with 2 units and Sigmoid activation, producing predicted arousal and valence values in [0, 1].

The model was compiled with the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy loss. The training went through 30 epochs with a batch size of 32, using a training and validation ratio of 80/20. Early stopping and reduction on plateaus were set as training callbacks, with early stopping having patience of 5 epochs and learning rate of 0.5 with patience of 3.

Fig. 4. BiLSTM model architecture diagram. The network flows from Input Layer through two stacked Bidirectional LSTM layers (96 and 48 units), Dropout layers (rate = 0.3), Batch Normalization, Dense layers (128 and 64 units, ReLU), to a 2-unit Sigmoid output layer predicting arousal and valence.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Training Dynamics

Figure 5 shows the training and validation accuracy and loss graphs for 30 epochs. Both the accuracy graphs converge very quickly within the first five epochs, and by epoch 3, the validation accuracy has reached 95%. There is no question about the generalization capacity of the model; the validation accuracy closely follows the training accuracy, and the validation loss remains close to or even lower than the training loss in the latter epochs. There is no trace of any overfitting behavior throughout the entire training period. At the end of 30 epochs, the training accuracy and validation accuracy are at 99.1% and 98.9%, respectively.

Fig. 5. Training history over 30 epochs. Left: accuracy. Right: training loss.

B. Classification Performance and Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix presented in Figure 6 shows the number of predictions for each individual class based on the whole test data set (approximately 46,500 samples). High values are noted for both precision and recall for all four quadrants that constitute emotions. Low Arousal, Negative Valence has 14,957 accurate predictions with only 105 prediction errors (0.70% error rate). Low Arousal, Positive Valence makes 8,192 predictions correctly while committing just 18 errors (0.22%). High Arousal, Negative Valence has 8,173 correct predictions with 38 predictions being erroneous (0.46%). Lastly, High Arousal, Positive Valence makes 14,873 predictions correctly with 188 prediction errors (1.24%), which constitutes the highest individual error rate, mostly because of confusion with the Low Arousal, Positive Valence. The overall test accuracy is 98.96%.

Fig. 6. Confusion Matrix of the BiLSTM Classifier Trained on the Held-Out Test Set (~46,500 samples). The diagonal elements

depict correct classifications by each class, while the off-diagonal elements denote misclassification between emotion quadrants.

C. Comparative Model Evaluation

Figure 8 shows an accuracy comparison of four models—Logistic Regression, Random Forest, SVM, and MLP; where all are trained on the 110-dimensional handcrafted feature vector. Random Forest achieves the highest performance among the classical baselines with both test and validation accuracy of 99.9%, nominally exceeding the BiLSTM. This result should, however, be interpreted with care: the Random Forest operates on richly engineered aggregate statistics that implicitly condense temporal information, whereas the BiLSTM learns directly from raw temporal sequences. The Random Forest’s advantage is therefore partly attributable to the information encoding of the feature engineering step rather than model expressiveness alone. Logistic Regression (97.9% / 97.8%) and MLP (94.9% / 94.9%) provide strong additional baselines; SVM (91.1% / 91.3%) underperforms the other methods at this dataset scale.

Fig. 8. Model performance comparison bar chart. Test accuracy (blue) and validation accuracy (orange) are displayed side-by-side for Logistic Regression (97.9%), Random Forest (99.9%), SVM (91.1%), and MLP (94.9%).

D. Feature Importance Analysis

Figure 7 reports the top 20 most important features identified by the Random Forest classifier using the Gini impurity criterion. Feature_109 (importance: 0.204) and Feature_108 (0.200) together account for over 40% of the total model importance, suggesting that the terminal components of the 110-dimensional feature vector—likely corresponding to late-window MFCC coefficients or spectral envelope descriptors—are highly discriminative for emotion quadrant separation. Feature_107 (0.128) and Feature_101 (0.098) continue to highlight the significance of these features within a smaller number. Such a large skew indicates that there is great potential to achieve high

performance levels by reducing the feature set without increasing the computational load.

Fig. 7. Top 20 features in order of decreasing importance using the Random Forest Gini index. Features 109 and 108 have Gini index values of 0.204 and 0.200, respectively, and they contribute more than 40% to the overall importance of the model.

V. DISCUSSION

Among the observations made due to the experimental analysis is the following: the performance accuracy achieved by the BiLSTM model is comparable to those of traditional machine learning algorithms using heavily engineered feature vectors.

However, one of the main strengths of the BiLSTM method is its ability to directly analyse the time-based signal; it is important in the music domain because emotions are created through melody development, rhythm and timbre change.

Second, the clustering of Random Forest feature importance on a few features (in particular, Feature_108 and Feature_109) is a surprising and practically relevant result. This finding calls for further research on how to explain the acoustical characteristics of those highly important features as well as how to create a far simpler feature set while maintaining the same discriminability.

Third, the use of Azure OpenAI in the process of creating therapeutic insight is a qualitatively new step beyond conventional MER systems. Not only does the model classify emotions into specific categories but it also provides insights on how to address such emotions through music.

It should be emphasized that although the arousal-valence model is sound from a psychological perspective, it is an oversimplification of the true nature of human emotions. Music may stimulate several emotions at once, and the borders between the quadrants in the A-V plane are ambiguous. The decision to utilize such a coarse categorization strategy in this work represents a sacrifice of psychological realism for technical feasibility.

VI. APPLICATIONS

There are multiple fields where the Swar Manovigyan concept can find its practical application. Firstly, clinical psychology and music therapy would benefit from using the system to have an objective evaluation of emotions involved into the musical process, making possible to choose or adjust music according to the desired emotional state of clients. Secondly, as far as consumer technologies are concerned, the system can be the emotional intelligence component to make mood adaptive playlists based on the actual emotional state of the user.

In addition, the system is a great tool for mental well-being checks, being completely non-invasive and non-intrusive because it does not require any sensors or devices; only smartphones and web browsers are needed to implement it. The application of this technology to mental health monitoring in educational institutions can be a good solution in providing accessible emotional wellness resources for students.

Lastly, AI-generated conclusions about therapy may prove effective psychoeducation material.

VII. LIMITATIONS

However, several weaknesses that exist in the current work need mentioning. To begin with, the crowd-sourced labels in terms of arousal and valence contain inherent bias in relation to individual perception of music. Emotions aroused by music are personal and can be different in various cultural contexts; hence, the model detects population patterns of emotional behaviour, not individual reactions.

Furthermore, the proposed method is currently able to analyse either whole songs or windows with fixed size. There can be significant changes in emotion throughout the song, and the ability to perform streaming analysis could be beneficial in such cases.

Moreover, the therapeutic suggestions provided by the language model are not validated in a clinical setting and are intended to illustrate general rules of psychology, rather than replace professional evaluation.

Finally, the dataset used to train the model consists largely of Western popular music. Hence, the question arises whether the developed model will be equally effective when applied to Indian classical music, jazz, and folk tunes, among others.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

There are several areas for further research that arise out of this study. The first and foremost among these is the use of continuous, segment-level emotion analysis, wherein the algorithm analyses sequential segments of audio in real-time and tracks the emotional trajectory throughout the entire listening experience. This can be used to implement music recommendation systems driven by biofeedback.

From a technical perspective, inclusion of attention mechanisms or even transformer architectures trained on audio spectrograms might lead to better selective attending of emotional parts of the spectrogram by the model. Training the architecture in a self-supervised manner on large unannotated audio datasets and then fine-tuning it on the emotion's dataset seems like a promising direction towards improvement of generalization capability without adding any new annotated data. Personalization with a user-specific model, ideally using federated learning to maintain patient anonymity, would make the application much more useful both for patients and researchers.

IX. CONCLUSION

Swar Manovigyan is an efficient deep learning model developed in this paper for addressing the problem statement of integrating music emotion recognition with the domain of mental health. It utilizes a pipeline of mel-spectrogram extraction from raw audio files, classification of emotions belonging to one of four quadrants in an arousal-valence plane using a BiLSTM architecture, and context generation for insights related to mental health by the incorporation of LLMs.

The BiLSTM network is highly discriminatory with a test accuracy of 98.96%. The comparison with classical machine learning models further substantiates the efficiency of the model proposed.

In conclusion, it is evident that using music emotion recognition along with explanation generation through generative AI and web technologies can provide a reliable, efficient, and non-invasive way of emotional analysis and help with mental well-being. The Swar Manovigyan project contributes not only to the field of affective computing but also shows a responsible use of AI-based solutions in mental health care.

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